

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Kadirova Marguba Buriyevna

SELECTION OF GRAMMAR MATERIAL IN ENGLISH IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/MAY

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MENTION
★ ★ ★ ★ ★

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